

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses innovative teaching technologies in educational institutions.

Keywords: innovation, technology, education, training, module.

The introduction of modern information technologies that meet international educational standards, as well as providing all the necessary conditions for the fruitful work of teachers, teachers, masters of industrial training are strategic priorities in the field of education. After all, information technologies help teachers to bring the educational process to a qualitatively new level.

Today, many teachers use modern technologies and innovative teaching methods in order to achieve learning effectiveness. These methods include active and interactive forms used in teaching. Active ones provide for an active position of the student in relation to the teacher and to those who receive education with him. During the lessons with their application, textbooks, notebooks, a computer are used, that is, individual means used for teaching. Thanks to interactive methods, there is an effective assimilation of knowledge in cooperation with other students. These methods belong to collective forms of teaching, during which a group of students works on the studied material, while each of them is responsible for the work done [1, p. 10].

The word “innovation” (from the Latin “innovation”) appeared in the middle of the 17th century and means the entry of a new into a certain sphere, implantation into it and the generation of a number of changes in this sphere. Innovation is, on the one hand, the process of innovation, implementation, implementation, and on the other hand, it is an activity to develop innovation into a certain social practice, and not a subject at all. Innovation in the exact translation from Latin does not mean “new”, but “into the new”. The concept of “innovation” means innovation, novelty, change; innovation as a means and process involves the introduction of something new. In relation to the pedagogical process, innovation means the introduction of new things into the goals, content, methods and forms of education and upbringing, the organization of joint activities of the teacher and the student.

The emergence of new information technologies associated with the development of computer tools and telecommunications networks has made it

possible to create a qualitatively new information and educational environment as a basis for the development and improvement of the education system.

Methods of innovative learning – modular learning, problem-based learning, distance learning, research methodological training, project method, social partnership, etc.

Interactive methods contribute to the qualitative assimilation of new material.

These include:

- exercises of a creative nature;
- group tasks;
- educational, role-playing, business games, imitation;
- lessons-excursions;
- lessons-meetings with creative people and specialists;
- classes aimed at creative development
- lessons-performances, making films, publishing newspapers;
- use of video materials, internet, visibility;
- solving complex issues and problems using the methods of “decision tree”, “brainstorming”.

The main goal of innovative educational technologies is to prepare a person for life in an ever-changing world. The goal of innovation activity is a qualitative change in the student's personality compared to the traditional system.

Therefore, innovative teaching methods contribute to the development of cognitive interest in students, teach them to systematize and generalize the studied material, discuss and discuss. Comprehending and processing the acquired knowledge, students acquire the skills to apply them in practice, gain communication experience.

Undoubtedly, innovative teaching methods have advantages over traditional ones, because they contribute to the development of the child, teach him independence in cognition and decision-making.

Also, innovative teaching methods provide interactive learning. It is aimed at active and deep assimilation of the studied material, the development of the ability to solve complex problems. Interactive activities include simulation and role-playing games, discussions, modeling situations. One of the modern methods is learning through collaboration. It is used to work with social partners, as well as in small groups. This method aims at the effective assimilation of educational material, the development of the ability to perceive different points of view, the ability to cooperate and resolve conflicts in the process of teamwork. Innovative methods have made it possible to change the

role of the teacher, who is not only a carrier of knowledge, but also a mentor who initiates creative searches of students [2, p. 23].

In this regard, the education system should aim at the formation of a new type of specialist who would be able to independently extract, process, analyze the necessary information and use it effectively at the right moment. This can be achieved with the transition to multi-level training of highly qualified specialists (bachelor - master - doctor).

A new organization of society, a new attitude to life also impose new requirements on the school. Today, the main purpose of training is not only the accumulation of a certain amount of knowledge, skills, and skills by a student, but also the preparation of a student as an independent subject of educational activity. Modern education is based on the activity of both the teacher and, no less importantly, the student. It is precisely this goal - the upbringing of a creative, active person who knows how to learn, improve independently, and the main tasks of modern education are subordinated to.

An innovative approach to learning allows you to organize the learning process in such a way that the lessons are a joy to the student, and brings benefits, without turning into just fun or a game. And, perhaps, it is at such a lesson, as Cicero said, "the eyes of the listener will light up about the eyes of the speaker".

Innovative technologies:

1. Gaming
2. project
3. technology of problem-based learning
4. technology of differentiated learning
5. technology of educational and research activities in the classroom.

Educational innovative technologies:

1. health-saving technologies
2. group activity technology
3. CCA technology (collective creative affairs).

The relevance of innovative learning is as follows:

- compliance with the concept of humanization of education;
- overcoming formalism, authoritarian style in the teaching system;
- the use of personality-oriented learning;
- search for conditions for the disclosure of the creative potential of the student;
- compliance of the socio-cultural needs of modern society with independent creative activity.

The main objectives of innovative learning are:

- development of intellectual, communicative, linguistic and creative abilities of students;
- formation of personal qualities of students;
- development of skills that affect educational and cognitive activity and transition to the level of productive creativity;
- development of different types of thinking;
- formation of high-quality knowledge, skills and abilities.

These goals also define the tasks of innovative learning:

- optimization of the educational process;
- creating an environment of student-teacher cooperation;
- development of long-term positive motivation for learning;
- inclusion of students in creative activities;
- careful selection of the material and methods of its submission.

Innovative learning is based on the following technologies:

- developing training;
- problem-based learning;
- develop critical thinking;
- differentiated approach to learning;
- creating a situation of success in the lesson.

The main principles of innovative learning are:

- creativity (focus on creativity);
- assimilation of knowledge in the system;
- non-traditional forms of lessons;
- use of visibility.

And now I want to move from the general methodological principles of innovative learning to methods. When using innovative technologies in teaching English language and literature, the following techniques are successfully applied:

- associative series;
- reference summary;
- brain attack;
- group discussion;
- essay;
- key terms;
- videos;
- didactic game;
- linguistic maps;

- text research;
- working with tests;
- non-traditional forms of homework, etc.

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